

Preparation of Triethyl 2-Methyl-5-isopropylpentane-1,2,5-tricarboxylate

D. N. Mukherji

As the method described by Bardhan *et al.*¹ did not provide satisfactory yield of triethyl 2-methyl-5-isopropylpentane-1,2,5-tricarboxylate (I), a different method was adopted to obtain promising yield of the compound.

Following Lapworth and McRea², ethanolic potassium cyanide was added to diethyl 1-cyano-2-methylpent-1-ene-1,5-dicarboxylate (II), prepared according to Banerjee³. The resultant product, diethyl 1,2-dicyano-2-methylpimelate (III), on acid hydrolysis, decarboxylation, and esterification afforded the ester (IV).

Condensation of the ester (IV) with diethyl oxalate⁴, followed by elimination of carbon monoxide, produced tetraethyl 2-methylpentane-1,2,5,5-tetracarboxylate (V) which on isopropylation afforded (VI). Hydrolysis and decarboxylation of (VI) furnished 2-methyl-5-isopropylpentane-1,2,5-tricarboxylic acid (VII) as a crystalline solid, crude m.p. 135-36°, which after crystallisation from hydrochloric acid had m.p. 140-41°. The previous authors¹ (reported m.p. 135-36°) do not seem to have obtained it in a state of purity. The acid was also prepared according to Bardhan *et al.*¹ for comparison and was found to have the same melting point, 140-41°; it showed no depression on admixture. The desired ester (I) was ultimately obtained by esterification of the above acid by alcohol vapour method.

1. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 3195.

2. *Ibid.*, 1922, 121, 2752.

3. *This Journal*, 1940, 17, 453.

Triethyl 2-Methylpentane-1,2,5-tricarboxylate (IV).—An ethanolic solution of diethyl 1-cyano-2-methylpent-1-ene-1,5-dicarboxylate (II) (25.3 g.) was mixed with a solution of 93% potassium cyanide (11 g.) in water (25 ml). It became slightly warm at the start and the mixture was kept at room temperature for 4 days. The solution was then evaporated to dryness. The residual mass was heated with HCl (conc., 250 ml) and then refluxed for 30 hours. The mass on evaporation and extraction with acetone yielded 22 g. of crude tricarboxylic acid, m.p. 149-50° which crystallised from HCl (conc.) in short prisms, m.p. 152°. The acid, thus obtained, was heated with absolute ethanol (50 ml) and H_2SO_4 (conc., 5 ml) at 110-15° in a current of ethanol vapour for 6 hours. The ester (IV), thus obtained (25 g.), distilled constantly at 162-65°/6mm as a colorless mobile oil. (Found: C, 59.43; H, 8.56. $C_{13}H_{26}O_6$ requires C, 59.6; H, 8.6%.)

Tetraethyl 2-Methylpentane-1,2,5,5-tetracarboxylate (V).—Super dry (over Ca) ethanol (2.5 g.) in dry ether (6 ml) was added dropwise to a well-cooled suspension of finely divided potassium (2.2 g.) in dry ether (60 ml). After the disappearance of potassium, diethyl oxalate (8 g.) was added slowly. The ester (IV) (14 g.) was then added dropwise to the cold solution and left for 24 hours. Finally it was diluted with ice-water and worked up in the usual way. The tetracarboxylate (11 g.) was obtained as a colorless distillate, b.p. 184-85°/5mm. (Found: C, 57.81; H, 8.26. $C_{18}H_{32}O_8$ requires C, 57.75; H, 8.28%.)

Tetraethyl 2-Methyl-5-isopropylpentane-1,2,5-tetracarboxylate (VI).—The preceding ester (V) (30 g.) was added to a cooled mass of sodium ethoxide, prepared from sodium (1.0 g.) and absolute ethanol (32 ml), followed by isopropyl iodide (25 g.) added all at a time, and the mixture was refluxed for 20 hours on a steam bath in a soda water bottle. The ester was worked up in the usual way to provide the ester (VI, 29 g.) as a colorless distillate, b.p. 188-89°/3 mm. (Found: C, 60.4; H, 8.65. $C_{24}H_{46}O_8$ requires C, 60.4; H, 8.5%.)

2-Methyl-5-isopropylpentane-1,2,5-tricarboxylic Acid (VII).—The ester (VI) (29 g.) was hydrolysed by refluxing on a sand bath for 16-18 hours with HCl (conc., 145 ml). The clear solution obtained was evaporated to dryness on a water bath; the dry mass was extracted with ether to yield the crude acid (18 g.), m.p. 135-36°. On crystallisation from HCl, the acid melted at 140-41°. (Found: C, 55.5; H, 7.6. Calc. for $C_{12}H_{22}O_6$: C, 55.4; H, 7.7%.)

Triethyl 2-Methyl-5-isopropylpentane-1,2,5-tricarboxylate (I).—The acid (20 g.), thus obtained, was esterified by alcohol vapour method by heating at 110° for 6 hours. The tricarboxylic ester (25 g.) was obtained as a colorless viscous oil which distilled constantly at 174°/4 mm. (Found: C, 62.7; H, 9.4. Calc. for $C_{18}H_{32}O_6$: C, 62.8; H, 9.3%). Further studies with the ester (I) are in hand.